

Buddhist and Deep Ecological approaches as a new path to Environmental Sustainability

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Abstract: *Buddhism and Deep Ecology can be considered as the spiritual dimensions of the environment. Buddha's teachings are related to Deep Ecology which aims at protecting natural forests and the environment. They are considered as oneness, awareness, compassion, loving, kindness towards all living beings. Both are approached on a holistic outlook and consciousness. Buddhism and Deep Ecology are basically concerned with change. Deep Ecology fosters a moral awareness of the kinship of the natural environment. It is concerned with the survival and self-renewal of all living beings. Deep Ecology reflects an awareness and concern about the intrinsic value of all living beings and the integrity of their natural home, along with a sense of the limits of the human role in the scheme of things. The awareness and concern of Deep Ecology towards nature offers new approach on values which reflect oneness of all life. This paper explores the interaction of Deep Ecology with Buddhist principles and ethics proposing an awareness of nature as a new path to sustainable future which greatly contributes to one's understanding imagination, and reinvigoration for activism and education.*

Keywords: *Buddhism, Deep Ecology, Change, Sustainable environment*

Introduction: The most complicated problems which are gradually increasing day by day are environmental issues. Widespread natural calamities, calamities exacerbated by pollution, unpredicted weather condition have severely disturbed human existence. All of these natural abnormalities have threatened human life and livelihood. Worldwide thinkers are serious about these environmental problems and have redefined the man and nature relationship. Human beings survive among multitude of plants, animals and inanimate natural objects. Humans are deeply reliant on natural resources. But gradual development of science and technology have governed the forces of nature causing environmental disasters. Nature is apprehended as a machine for the use of human cause. All moral considerations are applied to man only. This is the attitude that differentiates man from the rest of the nature. The root cause of this attitude is the anthropocentric ideology developed in the western world.

Traces of anthropocentric attitude can be found in as early as Greek tradition like Pythagoras, the Greek philosopher declared 'homomensura' i.e. man is the measure of all things. Aristotle also presents a demeaning picture of the environment and its relation to human beings. The doctrine of anthropocentrism states that man is the only significant or important being in this world. He is the centre of the universe. All other beings depend on humanbeings for their significance. All the things are valuable only if and only if they are of use to human beings. The non-anthropocentric attitude thrived because of the selfish attitude of anthropocentrism. Non anthropocentric attitude rejects the views of anthropocentrism that humans are masters of nature and nature is there to be exploited by him. It develops an approach that is not based on what benefits individual or human community as a whole, but what benefits the biotic community as a whole. Non anthropocentric attitude recognizes the intrinsic worth of every being and object of nature. It is based on nature-centered morality, rather than human-centered morality.

Objectives: This research aims to:

1. To explore deep ecology's ethics emphasizing the inherent worth and rights of the nature.
2. To analyze Buddhist ethical principles with Deep Ecology for a sustainable environment.
3. To promote a holistic outlook and consciousness of the natural environment shifting from anthropocentric to eco centric concern.

Methodology: This study is analytical and descriptive. Data sources are collected from various published books and journals.

Discussion: Sustainable development represents a commitment for the well-being of the humans by promoting development of the ecological limits of the biosphere. It produces an ideal balanced ecosystem. Environmental ethics is merely one aspect of ethics in sustainability. It deals with the relationship between human beings and nature and is a subset of ethics and sustainability. It considers the complex relationships between humans, the environment and the economy both for current populations and future generations. Sustainability in environmental ethics is responsible for conserving natural resources and protecting global ecosystems. Ecology is the study of ecosystem. Ecology refers to the science of the interrelationships among organisms and their environment. Due to the tremendous development of ecological science, ecocentrism was established. This attitude developed according to which the whole ecosphere is the centre of moral valuation or right claim. Ecocentrism finds inherent value in all of nature. It goes beyond biocentrism by including environmental systems as wholes, and their abiotic aspects. Ecocentrism holds that nature has intrinsic value and advocates for ecological well-being. This attitude contrasts with anthropocentrism, which places humans at the center of all value and consideration. Tied in with the concept of ecocentrism is Deep Ecology. Deep Ecology is an environmental philosophy that proposes an embracing of ecological ideas and environmental ethics regarding how humans should relate to nature. Arne Naess developed the concept of deep ecology according to which nature should be valued independent of its ability to be used for human welfare. Deep Ecology's core principle is the belief that the living environment as a whole should be respected. Deep Ecologists preserved the integrity of the biosphere for its own sake, irrespective of the possible benefits to humans. It represents a coherent world where all human beings, species, animals, inanimate objects are the part and parcel. Each part is valuable according to its own sphere. No one is positioned higher nor lower.

Likewise, Buddhism offers a well-developed philosophy of our connection with nature. Buddhism needs to be examined in the light of current ecological crisis and to generate ethical world views that underline fundamental attitudes and values of different cultures and societies. Buddhism presents an awareness of nature through inter relatedness, oneness, loving, kindness and compassion for all living beings. Buddhism believes in the theory of impermanence which means everything is changing, rising and falling away. Everything that happens depends upon the mind and conditioning. Buddhism focuses on the extinction of suffering which causes by attachment merely through ignorance or Avidya. To stop attachments, Buddhism offers the eight-fold noble path of right understanding: right faith, right resolve, right speech, right action, right living, right effort, right thought and right concentration.

Dhamma and Deep Ecology: Buddhism is basically Dhamma or Dharma

that has two inter related areas that is Buddha's teachings and the laws of Nature that apply to all life. Buddha's teachings include compassion, loving, kindness and respect for all living beings. The blessings of Buddhists often state, "May all beings be happy," and "May all beings be peaceful". Dhamma or Dharma in nature basically means that human beings exist and survive amongst all living beings. There are also laws in nature like impermanence, that operate and apply to nature. Many of these values and laws from Dhamma or Dharma can be cor-related with Deep Ecology. There is a close relationship between Dhamma and Deep Ecology.

The Dhamma/ Dharma based on the teachings of Nature or the orientation of Buddhism toward nature, has numerous principles which correlate with Deep Ecology. As a highly respected world religion, Buddhism offers a great potential for influencing people in their thought, values and behaviour towards ecological sustainability of nature. The ecosystem is subject to impermanence or change as well as the laws of nature or Dhamma. Succession involves change or impermanence. From an ecological standpoint, succession involves an orderly sequence of change, with biotic components succeeding one another over a period of time in a given area. Both Buddhism and Deep Ecology are basically concerned with change. Such change is based along clear and realistic lines contained both within Buddhism and Deep Ecology. Both concepts have similar views as they use values and perspectives that are based on spiritual and holistic principles for positive change in paradigms, attitudes, and practices for conservation of natural environment. They present a holistic, spiritual, cultural approach to environmental problems and degradation.

Spiritual values: Buddhism and Deep Ecology can be considered as the spiritual dimensions of the environment. Buddha's teachings are related to Deep Ecology which aims at protecting natural forests and the environment. They are considered as oneness, awareness, compassion, loving, kindness towards all living beings. Both are approached on a holistic outlook and consciousness. Deep Ecology fosters a moral awareness of the kinship of the natural environment. It is concerned with the survival and self-renewal of all living beings. Deep Ecology reflects an awareness and concern about the intrinsic value of all living beings. This doctrine calls for a paradigm shift from anthropocentric to ecocentric. The awareness and concern of Deep Ecology towards nature offers new approach on values which reflect oneness of all life. The interaction of Deep Ecology with Buddhist principles and ethics greatly contributes to one's understanding, imagination, and reinvigoration for activism and education.

Conclusion: Man cannot be separated from his social and physical environment. Buddhism emphasizes interconnectedness and interdependence of all beings and nature. It provides a basis for an environmental ethics since it deals with the concern for nature as well as human beings. We should reconsider our own immoral activities in order to be for our best environmental behaviour. The self-realization of Deep Ecology and the interdependence tenet of Buddhism and ecology help humans go beyond anthropocentric consciousness. The personal-self becomes an ecological-self and comes to include all other beings and the planet itself. This breaks the illusion that we humans are different from the rest of nature. All the components of the nature work together in complete coordination for the wellbeing of the whole unit. Humans or society who use and manage the environment have also responsibility to preserve the environment. Nature benefits humans in various ways. But in terms of taking advantage and using it, humans require

awareness of the responsibility in maintaining and utilizing it in the long term.

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